

Legal aspects of HET: Spain

[WP3 – Human enhancement]

Lead contributor	Javier Valls Prieto, University of Granada jvalls@ugr.es
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Executive summary

This country report of Spain is divided in six sections.

The introduction has a brief summary of the Spanish law system, the objective of the report, the methodological approach and the state of the art of legislative work in the Parliament.

The next step is the scope and limitations of this report. The task designated in the SIENNA project has a limitation of time (0.6 PM) so the work was done under this premise.

The third part is about legal development. The two questions related to the state of the art of law and HE. The research is about what law and human right are affected right now within the HE development, if there is any motion to try to adapt the legal system, how the Courts have solve the case law and, the last one, to identify any future law development about the topic. The key point to answer these questions is to find the legal corpus that can address the questions about the HETs. Sometimes was possible to find it but others there is no specific Act that regulate the question asked. Only for the definition of the concept health was needed to look for eight different Acts and several case-law of the Constitutional and Supreme Court. Finally we could found it in the new regulation about sexual health and reproduction Act. After the research the result was not fruitful but we can say there are solutions to the problems that can come in the next years.

The part four spins around specific legal issues. How in Spain will be the impact of these technologies in fundamental rights in the Constitution. In Spain there is no special regulation on HE but the general system, Fundamental Rights and the legislative corpus about health, can provide solutions to the actually problems on HE. It is necessary to go to these general norms to find solutions. In the case of drugs of prosthesis and device there are specific acts about the topic but there are not thinking on human enhancement, or the legislative power does not see a problem with it. The patients consent for health treatment can be used as well for HE treatments, there is no particular issues on that topic. Finally, the question about to augmented body, we have to say that is a concept that are not in the legal system and there is no way to link it to any actual Act in Spain.

The next point is to describe the discussion in Spain about the legal aspects in HE. This can be divided in two sections: how the HE will be impact on the legal praxis and how we can find solutions for the new legal problems the Spanish society is going to face with this technological revolution.

Finally there is a conclusion to the state of the art of the Spanish legal system actually and what we can expect in the near future.

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List of acronyms/abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
HE	Human Enhancement
HET	Human Enhancement Technologies
FDA	Food and Drug Administration
FDCA	Food, Drug, and Cosmetic Act
FR	Fundamental right. Have a direct defence by the Constitutional Court
PP	Programmatic principle. Political principle with no power at the Constitutional Court

Table 1: List of acronyms/abbreviations

List of national legislation

Rational Use and Guaranties of Medical Drugs and Products Act, 26 July 2006
Royal Decree on the Regulation of Sanitary Products, 16 October 2009
Biomedical Research Act, 3 July 2007
Act Project on Data Protection and Digital Rights Warranties, 2018
Special Measures in Health Act, 14 April 1986
Health Service General Act, 25 April 1986
Public Health General Act, 4 October 2011
Sexual and Reproduction Health and Voluntary Pregnancy Interruption Act, 3 March 2010
Royal Decree 1090/2015 on Clinical Trials with Drugs, Drugs Research Ethics Comities and the Spanish Register of Clinical Research, 4 December 2015
Royal Decree 1907/1996 over Publicity and Commercial Promotion of Product, Activities or Service with Health Aim and the Warranties, 2 August 1996
Rational Use of Drugs and Health Products Act, 26 July 2006
Royal Decree on the Specialized Medical Training, 7 February 2003
Royal Legislative Decree 1/2015 about the Guaranties and Rational Use of Drugs and Medical Products, 24 July 2015
Warranties and Rational Use of Drugs and Health Product Act, 24 July 2015
Criminal Code, 23 November 1995
Spanish Constitution, 29 December 1978
Rights and Duties in Materia of Information and Clinic Documentation and Patient's Autonomy Basic Act), 14 November 2002
Framework Statue of the Health Service Staff, 16 December 2003
Rights and Duties in Materia of Information and Clinic Documentation and Patient's Autonomy Basic Act, 14 November 2002
Special Measures in Public Health Act, 14 April 1986
Royal Decree on Intelctual Property, 12 April 1996

Table 2: List of national legislation

1. Introduction

Spain is a constitutional Estate with 17 autonomous communities (Galicia, Asturias, Cantabria, País Vasco, Navarra, Aragón, Cataluña, Castilla León, La Rioja, Madrid, Castilla la Mancha, País Valenciano, Baleares, Murcia, Extremadura, Andalucía y Canarias) and two autonomous cities (Ceuta y Melilla). The Constitution gives separate powers to the State and to the autonomous communities but in a few areas they share these powers as could be all topics related to medicine, environmental or taxes. The Constitution does not make provisions to regulate AI and robotics; they would be subject to field-specific applicable laws and regulations e.g., use of robotics in medicine.

In Spain there are four kinds of Acts, Ley Orgánica, Ley, Real Decreto Ley and Real Decreto Legislativo that come from the Parliament. Also we have norms that come from the Government (regulations) with different names, as could be Real Decreto, Orden ministerial or Orden de Comisión.

The **objective** of this report is to review the state of the law and current legal responses to developments in AI and robotics and determine how specific legal questions/issues are addressed in Spain.

The **methodology** used was a web scanner (google, Dialnet plus, Congreso de los Diputados and BOE¹) for laws, in the last ten years, that regulate the specific topics about HE that are developed in the State of the art in deliverable 3.1 of the SIENNA project and the result was that we found no one specific law. We have looked for, in Spanish, terms as “mejora humana”, “mejora cognitiva”, “medicamentos” “salud”, “salud en la legislación”, “bienestar”, “implantes”, “protesis” all of them with a combination with “legislación” and “regulación”) In google it was needed to add the term “España” to don’t get result linked to South American countries.

There are no Non-legislative Motions (Proposición no de ley)² to the Government to start the debate. We also asked select Spanish experts in the field of medicine and legal scholars and they gave us information about the relevant general health legislation.

2. Scope and limitations of the report

The HE legal debate in Spain does not exist nowadays. It is really complicated to find any information about these topics because the lack of information and legislative motions in the Parliament. The Government crisis in the last five years doesn’t make the best situation, with no a big majority, to face these challenges.

¹ Dialnet plus is a Law and social sciences web portal for journals and books <https://dialnet.unirioja.es/> BOE is the Official newspaper where all laws from Spain are published www.boe.es The official site of the Parliament (Congreso de los Diputados) gives information about the state of all legislative work in progress www.congreso.es

² This is a resource that the opposition parties can use at the Parliament to incite the Government to start a new regulation.

One of the biggest problem we have to face was the concept health. In Spanish health can be translated at least as “salud”, “sanitario” or “médico” and these three terms have a different hint that are not exactly the same meaning as the object of the report. In any case we have faced this problem trying to go to the idea behind the concepts and not the precise mean of the word. The scope is limited to the task 3.2. of the SIENNA Project.

3. Part I: Summary of legal developments and an analysis of national legal scholarship

3.1. Legal developments

Question 1

Have there been attempts or plans to adopt at national level new legislation or set up new regulatory bodies in response to new development and/or increased use of human enhancement technologies? Have there been/are there attempts to regulate how HETs are designed, set up, commissioned or used?

There is no national level legislation that regulate HET and there is no attempt to regulate or define this concept. Looking for terms as “medicamento” (drugs), “mejora humana” (human enhancement), “edición genética” (genetic editing), “cognitiva” (cognitive) in the web site of the Parliament³ we could find any proposal related to the topic. The only Non-legislative Motion found in the last year is about male contraceptive pill, presented by Podemos Party. The idea is that men can take the responsibility from contraception what release women from hormonal treatment, which is consider a human enhancement.

Depends on which area of HET are we talking about can be directed to different regulation as could be the Rational Use and Guaranties of Medical Drugs and Products Act, ref. 29/2006 and last time amended in 2015 (Ley de garantías y uso racional de los medicamentos y productos sanitarios)⁴ or the Royal Decree on the Regulation of Sanitary Products, ref. 1591/2009 (Real Decreto por el que se regulan los productos sanitarios)⁵. In the first Act, Title VI, regulates the rational use of drugs on humans that is limited to patients, that is in a medical treatment (article 81.2.d). In case of sell of drugs in a pharmacy, these drugs have to be sold as part of the therapeutic treatment. It is forbidden to sell drugs by telematics procedures and by regular mail (article 2.5). In the second Act, there are reference to implants. Article 11.7 says about the knee, hip and shoulder prosthesis that should have a function similar to a natural articulation. So we can understand that any implant for HE should be limited by the

³ www.congreso.es

⁴ Spain, Ley de garantías y uso racional de los medicamentos y productos sanitarios 29/2006 (Rational Use and Guaranties of Medical Drugs and Products Act), 26 July 2006, <https://www.boe.es/buscar/pdf/2006/BOE-A-2006-13554-consolidado.pdf>

⁵ Spain, Real Decreto por el que se regulan los productos sanitarios 1591/2009 (Royal Decree on the Regulation of Sanitary Products), 16 October 2009, <https://www.boe.es/boe/dias/2009/11/06/pdfs/BOE-A-2009-17606.pdf>

same idea. Article 33 of 1591/2009 Act has a list of different implant that must have an information label but it not a close list thus implant could be many things as could be a device, machine or robot.

About CRISPR there is no specific regulation at all and there is no intention to have a new law. Actually these kind of procedurals for humans are regulated by the Biomedical Research Act, from 2007⁶. Article 1 of this regulation says that human dignity and identity should protected with respect. This should be understand in the context of this act, that is to say, in a health environmental (article 1 and 2). The use of CRISPR outside this environmental is not allow. The human dignity and identity has to be understand as an individual right, no treatment should decrees the dignity and identity of a person but it would be possible to enhancement both, always in a health treatment. Although it not said and not prohibited we should understand that the limits stay at the normal human condition.

After a search in the web site of the parliament of legislative motions, there is no attempt to regulate any of HETs that we are studying in SIENNA at the moment.

Question 2

Have developments of HETs led to amendments in constitutional or human rights and/or legislation bearing on constitutional or human rights (for example the right to privacy, the right to bodily or mental integrity)? Please identify judgments of the highest national courts (constitutional or supreme courts) that address developments of HET.

We cannot say HETs led amendment or any legislation change related to human rights. There are critical issues related to constitutional rights (in Spain called fundamental rights FR). In Spain there are several FRs that can have a connection to HE.

In Art. 10.1 of the Spanish Constitution⁷ can be found the right to a personal dignity and free human development understood as the personal freedom to be what a person want to be, that means should treated not as an instrument but as an end him/herself⁸. Dignity right can be considered relative and difficult to precise, for that reason the normal approach to its material content is from the negative aspects, the absence of dignity, this negative aspect of dignity is considered an infringement of the right (when there is no dignity)⁹: it is easier to know when there is no dignity than the definition of this concept itself. Thus, it depends in which context it will have a different meaning.

Once we see the difficulty to understand the concept and the topic we are working with, we can say dignity, related to HETs, as the human being's quality that let them to have possess rights and this means the demand of collection of minimum that refer to humiliation verge and subhumanity

⁶ Spain, Ley de investigación biomédica 14/2007 (Biomedical Research Act), 3 July 2007, <https://www.boe.es/buscar/pdf/2007/BOE-A-2007-12945-consolidado.pdf>

⁷ Article 10.1: The human dignity, the inviolable and inherent rights, the free development of the personality, the respect for the law and for the rights of others are the foundation of political order and social peace.

English version of the Spanish Constitution can be found in

https://www.boe.es/legislacion/codigos/codigo.php?id=158_Constitucion_Espanola_____The_Spanish_Constitution_&modo=1

⁸ Prieto Álvarez, Tomás, *La dignidad personal*, Thomson-Civitas, Madrid, 2005, p.169.

⁹ Pascual Medrano, Amalia, "La dignidad humana como principio jurídico del ordenamiento constitucional español" in Chueca, R., *Dignidad humana y derecho fundamental*, Centro de estudios políticos y constitucionales, Madrid, 2015, p. 306

conditions¹⁰. In this context we can say that some HETs can have a direct impact in the personal dignity particularly for good and in other cases for bad.

One important impact is related to dignified death and not to extend the life when the conditions are considered as not dignity. The use of HETs to extend life will not be allowed but in the other size the use of this HETs could just ensure a dignified end for the person.

The second important article for our report, article 15 of the Spanish constitution¹¹, talks about the life right. This is under discussion if foetus should be protected or not. Embryos should not be protected by article but some doctrine considered them as a life in potency. The end of life the limits are the end of brain activity or cardiac pulse.

Art. 14 of the Spanish Constitution regulates the right to equality, therefore no discrimination principle is included in this principle¹². This article talks expressly about some kinds of discriminations: birth, race, sex, religion, opinion and, finally, let a door open to future ways of discrimination linked to any other personal or social condition or circumstance. This article does not prohibit all different of treat but only that one that discriminate¹³, thus, it is possible to use HET always when there is no discrimination. Thus a person could use it whether there is no discriminatory impact in other people e.g. hair implant or other cosmetic surgeries will be allowed but use of cognitive drugs in an exam to get better mark than others.

There is no many cases in the Constitutional Court about equality principle and health treatment. One of them was related to the possibility of to attend immigrants who have not got the resident status in Spain. With the economic crisis of the last ten years the state government has taken out all non-resident immigrant from the free public health system. In 2015 there was a change of Government in Valencia country Autonomous Community and the change the regional law to let all persons to go to the public health system. The State attorney appeal to the Constitutional Court to revoke this regional law. The Constitutional Court did go into the equality right because it considers the Autonomous Community has no competence to rule about a national competence, so it lose a good opportunity to get deeply into the point¹⁴.

Art. 43¹⁵ talks about a political principle on how Government decision should have in mind to regulate public health service, especially focus in how the public health system should operate: prevention

¹⁰ Ruiz Lapeña, Rosa María, “La dignidad y sus manifestaciones en el ordenamiento constitucional español” in Ricardo Luis Chueca Rodríguez, *Dignidad humana y derecho fundamental*, Centro de estudios políticos y constitucionales, Madrid, 2015, p. 337

¹¹ Article 15: Everyone has the right to life and to a physical and moral integrity, and may under no circumstances be subjected to torture or to inhuman or degrading punishment or treatment. The death penalty is hereby abolished, except as provided by military criminal law in times of war.

¹² Article 14: Spaniards are equal before the law and may not in any way be discriminated against on account of birth, race, sex, religion, opinion or any other personal or social condition or circumstance.

¹³ Naranjo de la Cruz, Rafael “Derechos fundamentales” in Miguel Agudo Zamora et al. *Manual de Derecho Constitucional*, Tecnos, Madrid, 2018, p. 463.

¹⁴ Constitutional Court Sentence, STC 145/2017, 14 December 2017.

¹⁵ Article 14: 1. The right to health protection is recognised.

2. It is incumbent upon the public authorities to organise and safeguard public health by means of preventive measures and the necessary benefits and services. The law shall establish the rights and duties of all concerned in this respect.

measures, service needs and benefices. Finally announces, that Government will provide health education, sport and facilities the proper use of leisure and free time. This principle has two sides: a) the preventive health or collective health and b) the individual right. So the Government has to have an active power to avoid illness and the citizen have the right to get medical treatment¹⁶. Particularly important for HE is that it could be understood that is compulsory for the Government to promote HET in prevention of illness and leisure and free time.

Privacy right in Spanish constitution is regulated under article 18¹⁷. This year there is another decision of the Constitutional Court about article 18 (1) where honour, personal and family privacy and self-image. The same article in paragraph 4 limits the use of computer use and data processing to protect this right, a particular sensitive area for HETs that use devices with personal data as could be blood pressure, heart rate, and other vital constants. The Constitutional Court said in this case that there limitation of the use of algorithm in connection to the right to be forgotten. From 23rd November 2018 there is a new Data Protection and Digital Rights Warranties¹⁸.

The search of case law has no result. It has been used Thomson Reuters research motor and the term “Mejora cognitiva”, “mejora humana”, “CRISPR” in the case law from the Supreme Court and Constitutional Court. Also the research has been done by Acts but the results were really disappointed. No result found.

3.2. Legal scholarship

After a search in Dialnet¹⁹, the most important legal research data base in Spain, under the terms “mejora humana”, “mejora cognitiva” and “medicamento” plus “mejora humana” we have found very few reference related to the topic of the SIENNA project.

3. The public authorities shall promote health education, physical education and sport. Likewise, they shall encourage the proper use of leisure time.

¹⁶ Porras Nadales, Antonio, “Los principios rectores de la política social y económica” in Miguel Agudo Zamora et al. *Manual de Derecho Constitucional*, Tecnos, Madrid, 2018, p. 632

¹⁷ Article 18: 1. The right to honour, to personal and family privacy and to the own image is guaranteed.

2. The home is inviolable. No entry or search may be made without the consent of occupant or a legal warrant, except in case of flagrante delicto.

3. Secrecy of communications is guaranteed, particular of postal, telegraphic and telephonic communications, except the event of a court order to the contrary.

4. The law shall limit the use of data processing in order to guarantee the honour and personal and family privacy of citizens and the full exercise of their rights.

¹⁸ Spain, Proyecto de Ley orgánica de protección de datos y garantías de los derechos digitales (Act Project on Data Protection and Digital Rights Warranties), 2018,

http://www.senado.es/legis12/publicaciones/pdf/senado/bocg/BOCG_D_12_289_2209.PDF

¹⁹ <http://dialnet.unirioja.es>

The most interesting is related to human mental enhancement and criminal law limits. The main topic is if there is a way to control the intention of the criminals but it is a general work, more to describe the future possibilities than a legal study²⁰.

Sánchez Villanova exposes, in her PhD, the possibility of use of neurotreatment and neuroprediction to reduce of crime by cognitive interventions²¹.

Also, this year, has open the legal debate about the possibility of human enhancement by germinal line modification and how should be an international regulation that try to provide a solution to different cultures and legal tradition²².

About drugs the majority of the publications is about the administrative regulation of the drugs but there is nothing about the use of these drugs to human enhancement.

4. Part II: Analysis of specific legal issues

4.1. Terminology and legal demarcations

1. *Does the domestic law in your country provide a legal definition of “health” or the state of “health”? If yes, please quote the relevant source. Has the question of the definition of “health” been addressed in the case law?*

Art. 15 of the Spanish constitution talks about the life right. Art. 43 of the Spanish constitution says there is a right to protection of health but is not a FR but a political principle (PP) that means all new law should have in mind this principle but just as an interpretation principle. PPs have none direct protection from the Constitutional Court, thus is only and interpretation and political principle. This article also references to how the public health system should operate: prevention measures, service needs and benefices. Finally announces, that Government will provide health education, sport and facilities the proper use of leisure and free time.

In Spain there are three General Acts about health: Special Measures in Health Act, from 1986²³, (Ley Orgánica 3/1986 de medidas especiales en materia de salud), Health Service General Act, from 1986²⁴, (Ley 14/1986 General de Sanidad) and the Public Health General Act²⁵, last version from 2011 (Ley 33/2011 general de Salud Pública). In the first one there is no concept of health but the act itself talks

²⁰ Merkel, Reinhard, “Nuevas intervenciones en el cerebro. Mejora de la condición mental humana y límites del derecho penal” in Manuel Maroto Calatayud and Eduardo Demetrio Crespo, *Neurociencias y derecho penal*, Edisofer, Madrid, 2013, p. 7 ff.

²¹ Sánchez Vilanova, María, *¿Neuroimputabilidad? Una mirada interdisciplinar a la responsabilidad y tratamiento jurídico-penal de los trastornos de la personalidad desde los avances de la neurociencia*, Universidad de Valencia, Valencia, 2017.

²² García-Llerena, Viviana, “Tradiciones culturales como barreras para un bioderecho común: el caso de la mejora humana en línea germinal” in *Anales de la Cátedra Francisco Suárez*, n. 52, 2018, 155-178.

²³ Spain, Ley Orgánica de medidas especiales en materia de salud, 3/1986 (Special Measures in Health Act), 14 April 1986, <https://www.boe.es/buscar/pdf/1986/BOE-A-1986-10498-consolidado.pdf>

²⁴ Spain, Ley General de Sanidad 14/1986 (Health Service General Act), 25 April 1986, <https://www.boe.es/buscar/pdf/1986/BOE-A-1986-10499-consolidado.pdf>

²⁵ Spain, Ley General de Salud Pública, 33/2011 (Public Health General Act), 4 October 2011, <https://www.boe.es/boe/dias/2011/10/05/pdfs/BOE-A-2011-15623.pdf>

about illness, thus health is contrast of illness (article 1). In this precept the goal of public health is to prevent its lost or its worsening. Health is also when the health authorities implement measures of recognition, treatment, hospitalization or control of people (article 2). In the case of illness transmission can take preventive measures (article 3). In the second, that regulate the public health system and its administration, in article 1 and 2, referees to article 43 of the constitution to understand the scope of the act. In article 3 says all public health system is orientated to promote health and the prevention of illness. One more time health understood as the absence of illness. Finally, Article 1 of the Public Health General Act define public health as the activities organized by the public administration and society's collaboration to prevent illness. Otherwise there is no definition of the concept health in the law.

The only definition of health found in health legislation is the one in Sexual and Reproduction Health and Voluntary Pregnancy Interruption Act, from 2010²⁶, (Ley orgánica 2/2010 de salud sexual y reproductiva y de la interrupción voluntaria del embarazo). In article 3, this law consider health as the state of physical, mental and social complete wellness and not only the absence of complaint or illness.

The Autonomous Communities have the power to legislate about the administration of public health system. In the 17 Autonomous Communities none of them define the concept of health.

In the Constitutional Court case law, health is connected with the right to life and the physical and moral integrity²⁷ (moral has to be understood as psychic or mental)²⁸. In the case-law 5/2002 the Court²⁹ consider health as the right to not be damaged or put in risk the health of a HIV person who has to change from prison.

- 2. What are the basic legal terms and demarcations used nationally that should be taken into consideration in the discussion on the regulation of HET? Please consider the following dichotomies: medical v. non-medical, treatment v. enhancement, therapeutic v. non-therapeutic, natural v. non-natural. Are there any other potentially relevant legal demarcations or distinctions? Please provide a list of terms in the national language and an English translation (in case of doubt, please briefly explain the nature or source of doubts).*

The basic legal categories relevant to HETs used by existing law in Spain include:

²⁶ Spain, Ley Orgánica 2/2010 de salud sexual y reproductiva y de interrupción voluntaria del embarazo (Sexual and Reproduction Health and Voluntary Pregnancy Interruption Act), 3 March 2010, <https://www.boe.es/buscar/pdf/2010/BOE-A-2010-3514-consolidado.pdf>

²⁷ Escobar, Guillermo, "Informe presentado por la RCDP para el Informe General sobre el derecho a la salud presentado por la Red de Revistas de Derecho Constitucional en el XI Congreso Iberoamericano de Derecho Constitucional Jorge Carpizo, a celebrarse en Tucumán, Argentina, del 17 al 19 de septiembre de 2013", RCDP, 2013. <http://eapc-rcdp.blog.gencat.cat/2013/09/13/el-derecho-a-la-salud-en-la-jurisprudencia-del-tribunal-constitucional-espanol-guillermo-escobar/>

²⁸ Constitutional Court sentence STC 119/2001, 24 May 2001

²⁹ Constitutional Court sentence STC 5/2002, 14 January 2002

- Medical (or “therapeutic”) v. nonmedical (occasionally referred to as “wellness”)
- Health v. illness
- Medical practice (synonymous with “practice of medicine,” i.e. an act/conduct) vs. medical product (which can be a drug, device, or biologic)
- Medical products vs. “general wellness products”
- Therapeutic vs. non-therapeutic benefits

3. *What criteria are used to classify services, devices and products according to those categories?*

As Spain has a public health system, medical services are strongly regulated. All those concepts, cited above, are regulated by the General Health Act 14/1986, Royal Decree 1090/2015 on Clinical Trials with Drugs, Drugs Research Ethics Committees and the Spanish Register of Clinical Research³⁰, Royal Decree 1907/1996 over Publicity and Commercial Promotion of Product, Activities or Service with Health Aim and the Warranties³¹ and Rational Use of Drugs and Health Products Act, 29/2006³². Concepts as medical, health, illness, medical practice, medical products or therapeutics have a definition in different Acts or, at least, are used on them. The other ones, as non-medical, general wellness products or non-therapeutic benefits are not regulated but we can understand that are different as their opposites.

There are many grey zones between medical treatment and non-medical treatment. Non-therapeutic cosmetic surgeries are not regulated³³. There is a speciality on plastic surgeries³⁴ once the doctor has finished the medicine degree and has made the national exam to be a doctor but it is not illegal to do cosmetic surgeries without it.

Medical practice and medical product are separated by law. The first one is regulated by several acts, from which the General Health Act is the most important, whereas medical products are regulated by the Royal Legislative Decree 1/2015 about the Guaranties and Rational Use of Drugs and Medical Products³⁵. Drugs for human use is considered any substance or group of substance that has properties

³⁰ Spain, Real Decreto 1090/2015 por el que se regulan los ensayos clínicos con medicamentos, los Comités de Ética de la Investigación con medicamentos y el Registro Español de Estudios Clínicos (Royal Decree 1090/2015 on Clinical Trials with Drugs, Drugs Research Ethics Committees and the Spanish Register of Clinical Research), 4 December 2015, <https://www.boe.es/buscar/doc.php?id=BOE-A-2015-14082>

³¹ Spain, Real Decreto 1907/1996 sobre publicidad y promoción comercial de productos, actividades o servicios con pretendida finalidad sanitaria (Royal Decree 1907/1996 over Publicity and Commercial Promotion of Product, Activities or Service with Health Aim and the Warranties), 2 August 1996, <https://www.boe.es/buscar/doc.php?id=BOE-A-1996-18085>

³² Spain, Ley 29/2006, de 26 de julio, de garantías y uso racional de los medicamentos y productos sanitarios (Rational Use of Drugs and Health Products Act), 26 July 2006, <https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-2006-13554>

³³ <https://www.efesalud.com/cirugia-plastica-especialidad/>

³⁴ Spain, Real Decreto 139/2003, de 7 de febrero, por el que se actualiza la regulación de la formación médica especializada (Royal Decree on the Specialized Medical Training), 7 February 2003, <https://www.boe.es/boe/dias/2003/02/14/pdfs/A06026-06028.pdf>

³⁵ Spain, Real Decreto Legislativo 1/2015 por el que se aprueba el texto refundido de la Ley de garantías y uso racional de los medicamentos y productos sanitarios (Royal Legislative Decree 1/2015 about the Guaranties and Rational Use of Drugs and Medical Products), 24 July 2015, <https://www.boe.es/boe/dias/2015/07/25/pdfs/BOE-A-2015-8343.pdf>

to treatment or prevent human illness or that can be used or administrated in human beings with the aim to restore, correct or modify the physiological function in order to execute a pharmacological, immunologic or metabolic action or to establish a medical diagnosis (article 2.a).

Medical product is defined, in article 2.f, as any instrument, device, equipment, computer program, material or any other article to be uses in human beings with aims to: a) diagnosis, prevention, control, treatment or relief of an illness; b) diagnosis, control, treatment, relief of therapeutic of a injure or deficient; c) research, substitution or modification of an anatomy or a physiological process; and d) conception regulation; without executing its principal action by pharmacologic, immunologic o metabolic means.

Personal care product is any substance o mix of them that, not considered as a legal drug, medical product, cosmetic or biocide, are destined to by apply on the skin, teeth or body mucosae with the aim to hygiene or aesthetic or to eliminate or neutralize ectoparasitic (article 2.m).

Cosmetic product is any substance o mix of them destined to by contact apply on the superficial part of the human body or the teeth or the buccal mucosa with the only or principal mean of clean it, perfume it, change its aspect, protect it, keep it on good conditions or change the body odour (article 2.n).

In Spain there is no specific legal distinction between Therapeutic and non-therapeutic. General Health Act says that all public health service will be provided therapeutic treatment, promote health and prevention of illness (article 3) Royal Decree about Clinic Tests with Drugs, Drugs Research Ethics Committees and Spanish Register of Clinic Studies³⁶, in article 2.1 a) says the drug must have the aim to treat or preen an illness, thus we should understand that non-treatment are not regulated in Spain.

4.2 Right to integrity of the person, legal permissibility of non-therapeutic services on the human body

Question 1

Does the domestic law recognize the right to (physical and/or mental) integrity of the person? If yes, please provide a relevant citation. What are the limits to this right? Please provide examples. What criteria and values are considered to set those limits?

As we have comment above, article 15 of the Spanish Constitution give a right to life to any person. The debate from the first time was around the limits of life (particularly with abortion and the beginning of life, and euthanasia and finish of it). There is also another limit with article 10, person's dignity. This means that the constitution only care about a dignity life so euthanasia can be allowed and living will has a legal impact.

At the same time article 15 regulate the right of moral and physical integrity but linked to punishment (prohibition of torture and death penalty) but can be interpreted to particular medical treatment or other aspect of life. In the health system this right is considered that serious injures affect the integrity

³⁶ Spain, Real Decreto Legislativo 1/2015 por el que se aprueba el texto refundido de la Ley de garantías y uso racional de los medicamentos y productos sanitarios (Warranties and Rational Use of Drugs and Health Product Act), 24 July 2015, <https://www.boe.es/boe/dias/2015/07/25/pdfs/BOE-A-2015-8343.pdf>

of the person³⁷ (STC 35/1996, F. J. 3; STC 37/2011 F. J. 3). It is not necessary a real injures it is enough with a big risk.

The consent right of the patient can be considered as part of the right. In case of amputation or extirpation of an organ or sense the patient has to consent, even when it is a life or death proceed. In these cases if the patient can give his/her consent he/she can refuse to the treatment. Any obligation to have it against his/her will can be considered as an infringement of the right. Something similar happened to donation and transplant of an organ or with an abortion. In case of the sterilization of an incompetent, after an exploration of the person, a Judge can give the consent for this proceed. Finally, in case of research and investigation there is no cases but following the Oviedo Convention consent is need³⁸.

Question 2

How is the legality of enhancement procedures (understood as non-therapeutic interventions in the human body) established?

Therapeutic interventions are regulated in article 2 of the Especial Measures in Materia of Public Health Act mention it. The General Health Act establishes that Public health system will provide only treatment to combat illness (article 18.2) e.g. a reconstruction of a breast after a mastectomy will be cover by the public health system but a silicon breast implant will not if it no therapeutic intervention. Non-therapeutic interventions are either not regulated, e.g. General Health Act, or are sanctioned, e.g. article 74. C. d. of the Biomedical Research Act. Thus, there is a grey zone that have to be solved case by case.

Non-therapeutic interventions will be ruled by the freedom of contract. In case that the intervention could produce injuries in the human body, as could be cosmetic surgery, tattoos, piercings and similar, needs the consent of the person to avoid criminal responsibility. Article 147 of the criminal code considers a crime to cause a injure that diminish the corporal integrity or mental or physical health. This kind of injures will be prosecuted only when the victim report it to the authorities. In case of serious damages or the use of arms, instruments, objects, means, ways or methods particularly dangerous for life or health (article 148). In this case is not need the activity of the victim. Victim's consent will be token in consideration to reduce drastically the punishment if it is given freely, valid, conscious and expressly (Article 155). In the particular case of organ transplant, sterilization and gender change with victim's consent will not be punished (Article 156)³⁹. Private clinics are allowed by articles 35 and 36 of the Spanish Constitution. Article 35 let the workers the right to free choice of profession or trade and article 36 establishes that the law shall regulate the special features of the legal status of Professional Associations and the exercise of professions requiring academic degrees.

³⁷ Canosa Usera, Raúl L., "La protección de la integridad personal", *RDP*, 100, 2017, p. 281

³⁸ Canosa Usera, Raúl L., "La protección de la integridad personal", *RDP*, 100, 2017, p. 289

³⁹ Spain, Código penal (Criminal Code), 23 November 1995, <https://www.boe.es/buscar/pdf/1995/BOE-A-1995-25444-consolidado.pdf>

Title IV, Chapter II, regulate when public administrations could go to private clinics to solve problems in the public sector⁴⁰.

All non-therapeutic interventions are ruled by contract law. The procedures should be implemented by people with particular degree e. g. surgeries should be implemented by a specialist in medicine, tattoos and piercings should be done by a sanitary hygienist official. There is no regulation for Botox or silicone injections. Medical associations recommends to be done by dermatologist.

In any case, patient's explicit consent will be need to proceed with the enhancement procedures (see question 4)

Question 3

Are there limits to what non-therapeutic procedures can be performed on a human body? What criteria are used to establish those limits? What is the role of consent? Does the national law, case-law or legal doctrine provide any guidance on how risks and benefits of non-therapeutic procedures should be weighed and/or what is the acceptable level of risk in those cases?

Non-therapeutic procedures are not regulated or prohibited. The only limit found in the law is for the public health system that is allowed only to proceed in case of health treatment, understood as a treatment to promote health or the prevention of illness (Article 8 of General Health Act from 1896)

The consent of the patient is regulated by the Rights and Duties in Materia of Information and Clinic Documentation and Patient's Autonomy Basic Act from 2002⁴¹, (Ley 41/2002 básica reguladora de la autonomía del paciente y de derechos y obligaciones en materia de información y documentación clínica)

All action related to health services have to be consent by the patient or users. This consent has to be obtained after suitable informing and have to be by hand (article 2.2) The patient has the right to non-consent but it has be giving by hand. Breaking this right the health worker could be, depending of the risk and the gravity of the result, either fined or sanctioned that could be a suspension of work (article 70 and ff. of the Framework Statue of the Health Service Staff⁴²) or a prison penalty.

As non-therapeutic services are not regulated in any specific norm there is no national law, case-law related to this topics. To find a solution for cosmetic surgeries, tattoos, Botox, hair implant, etc. we need to use general regulation in civil code for contract law responsibility and in the case of injures to criminal law. Contract law responsibility can be found in articles 1.101-1.106 of the Civil Code and says that the parts of the contract will receive a compensation in case of damages or loss by intention of recklessness.

⁴⁰ Spain, Constitución Española (Spaish Constitution), 29 December 1978, <https://www.boe.es/buscar/pdf/1978/BOE-A-1978-31229-consolidado.pdf>

⁴¹ Spain, Ley 41/2002 básica reguladora de la autonomía del paciente y de derechos y obligaciones en materia de información y documentación clínica (Rights and Duties in Materia of Information and Clinic Documentation and Patient's Autonomy Basic Act), 14 November 2002, <https://www.boe.es/buscar/pdf/2002/BOE-A-2002-22188-consolidado.pdf>

⁴² Spain, Estatuto marco del personal sanitario (Framework Statue of the Health Service Staff), 16 December 2003, <https://www.boe.es/buscar/pdf/2003/BOE-A-2003-23101-consolidado.pdf>

Question 4

Is there a legal requirement for informed consent in the case of all non-therapeutic procedures? If yes, are requirements concerning informed consent more or less rigorous than in the case of procedures with a therapeutic aim?

All procedural in a person's body has to be consented except the cases of death of life situations. It is regulated under the Rights and Duties in Materia of Information and Clinic Documentation and Patient's Autonomy Basic Act from 2002⁴³. The Act doesn't make a distinction between therapeutic or non-therapeutic treatment. In case of e. g. to make a tattoo, there is a need of consent by hand as well as other cosmetic procedures to avoid criminal responsibility (see above question 4).

As both, therapeutic and non-therapeutic aim, are regulated by the same act and it makes no distinction between them, both procedures has the same rigorous. The limits are regulated in article 9 of the Rights and Duties in Materia of Information and Clinic Documentation and Patient's Autonomy Basic Act. The first one is when the patient does not want any information about the procedure. In this situation this right is limited by the patient's own health interest, by thirds person interested or by the collective interest and by the procedures itself. The second limit to the information right is when the collective interest of public health is in risk in one of the cases expressly marked by the Special Measures in Public Health Act, from 1986⁴⁴, always under a judge supervision in 24 hours after the decision. The third one is when there is an imminent physical or mental risk for the patient and it is not possible to ask for his/her consent. There also limits when the patient is underage or has no full cognitive abilities. In these cases a legal representative will take the decision always thinking on the best for the life or health of the patient.

Question 5

Has the question about the protection afforded to the augmented or modified body (e.g. body with prosthetics) been addressed nationally? Is the augmented or modified body (afforded the same protection and guarantees as an organic body)? Are there issues about ownership?

No, this question is not addressed in the Parliament.

Nowadays prosthetic are just legally consider as a normal body, there is no especial legal treatment. If we consider prosthetic as a health product, in a therapeutic treatment, it will be regulated under Warranties and Rational Use of Drugs and Health Product Act from 2006. But there is no special protection to the prosthetic. Last version of this Act is from 2015.

⁴³ Spain, Ley 41/2002 básica de derechos y obligaciones en materia de información y documentación clínica y autonomía del paciente (Rights and Duties in Materia of Information and Clinic Documentation and Patient's Autonomy Basic Act), 14 November 2002, <https://www.boe.es/buscar/pdf/2002/BOE-A-2002-22188-consolidado.pdf>

⁴⁴ Spain, Ley 3/1986 de medidas especiales en materia de salud pública, (Special Measures in Public Health Act), 14 April 1986, <https://www.boe.es/buscar/pdf/1986/BOE-A-1986-10498-consolidado.pdf>

The prosthetic will be considered as a regular thing under the patents and intellectual property law, nothing else. Royal Decree on Intellectual Property from 1996⁴⁵.

5. Discussion

Human enhancement in Spain, as itself, is not in the legal debate. What we can see looking at the vast world of medicine Acts is that something different as a health treatment rarely is regulated by the law and the exceptions we have found are only ban the different ways human enhancement can be presented.

In Spain we can make three distinctions: a) Human enhancement by treatment medicine; b) human enhancement by drugs; and c) human enhancement by prosthesis. After the legal research in human enhancement we could say that any of the three will not be allowed by the law in cases where this human enhancement makes a much better enhancement than the average people.

The use of drugs without a health necessity is not regulated but there is a double moral about its use. Wellness and cosmetic products have their own regulation, not as a health product for use in a medicine practice.

6. Conclusions

Human enhancement is not regulated in Spain. Some of the aspects of the SIENNA tasks can be partially found in the Health system legislation.

In the public health system HE treatment is not allowed. This kind of treatment in general is not regulated. The same happened with prosthesis. HE drugs and devices are regulated in any case. In particular all drugs, independent where they are for a health treatment or to HE, are covered by the Drugs Act. In case of drugs for HE are not allowed to sell them also by internet or mail. In practice they are sold without many problems. Wellness products, devices, etc. could be sold without problems. As HETs become more popular and developed, the Spanish law system needs a definition of HE and regulate many of the procedures that already are on a grey area where they are not regulated and in many cases are not prohibited. It is a challenge for the law system in the next years.

One of the problems is that, right now, it is more an ethical problem than a legal problem. Many of these procedures, drugs, devices or prostheses are not dangerous for the people and are not seen as risky for the rest of the population in Spain. So it is not an important point in the political and legislative agenda.

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